

Case Report

FULMINANT DESTRUCTIVE PAINLESS THYROID-ITIS AFTER A SINGLE DOSE OF PEMBROLIZUMAB IN AN OBESE ELDERLY MAN LOADED WITH IODINE

MARK CHAMBERS^{1,3}, MAZHAR KHAN¹, MAUREEN CHINWEZE^{1,*},
CONSTANCE CHEN², EDWARD FUA¹, SING-YUNG WU^{1,3}

¹Department of Radiology and Research, Veteran Administration University of California Irvine Medical Center, Long Beach, CA 90822

²Department of Medicine, University of California Irvine

³Department of Radiological Sciences, University of California Irvine, Irvine, CA 92697

*Corresponding author

Sing-yung Wu, M.D., Ph.D., Radiology and Research Service (151), VAUCI Medical Center, Long Beach, CA 90822, USA

Received: 24 May 2025

Accepted: 29 May 2025

Published: 10 June 2025

Copyright

© 2025 Sing-yung Wu

OPEN ACCESS

Abstract

Destructive thyroiditis can occur following the use of Pembrolizumab or an iodine loading from iodinated contrast administration, and topical application of iodinated skin preparations. Immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICI), commonly used in cancer patients, are often accompanied by frequent CT scans with iodinated contrast or surgeries involving topical iodine-based preparations, such as povidone-iodine (Betadine). Additionally, ICI-induced overt hyperthyroidism has been associated more frequently with higher body mass index. However, the combined impact of these factors on thyroid dysfunction in a single patient has not been previously reported.

We present the case of a 72-year-old obese male veteran with recurrent desmoplastic melanoma who developed rapidly progressive destructive thyroiditis following a single dose of Pembrolizumab. He received the therapy on day 0 and underwent repeated CT scans with iodinated contrast on days 8 and 35. Additionally, he had a recent excisional skin biopsy on his left forearm three days prior to Pembrolizumab administration (day -3).

He developed overt hyperthyroidism on day 22 (TSH = 0.03 μ U/mL, FT4 = 1.7 ng/dL) and peaked on day 29 post-ICI therapy (TSH = 0.01 μ U/mL, FT4 = 3.6 ng/dL). He remained hyperthyroid on day 51, then progressed to hypothyroidism by day 72 (TSH = 35.5 μ U/mL, FT4 = 0.3 ng/dL), worsening further by day 99 (TSH = 97.4 μ U/mL, FT4 = 0.1 ng/dL). The patient reported no thyroid pain and was initially reluctant to receive treatment. He maintained a normal heart rhythm, with a heart rate ranging from 67 to 103 bpm. Methimazole (10 mg/day) was administered for only two days (days 35 and 36), and levothyroxine replacement therapy was initiated on day 99.

The patient received only one dose of Pembrolizumab throughout the course of his thyroiditis. ICI therapy was resumed on day 159 following a cycle of radiation therapy (administered from day 10 to day 72). A PET/CT scan performed on April 6, 2020, revealed progression of right facial melanoma. He passed away three months later.

Abnormal thyroid function is associated with higher mortality and reduced life expectancy. Optimizing the metabolic state of cancer patients receiving ICIs may help reduce the incidence and severity of thyroid dysfunction, potentially improving overall survival and quality of life.

Introduction

Thyroiditis, inflammation of the thyroid gland, occurs in various forms [1]. The most common types include Hashimoto's thyroiditis, postpartum thyroiditis, painless and subacute thyroiditis. Less frequently, thyroiditis presents as acute suppurative thyroiditis or sclerotic chronic thyroiditis (Riedel's thyroiditis). Thyroiditis typically follows a triphasic pattern of thyroid dysfunction. Initially, patients experience hyperthyroidism (thyrotoxicosis) due to the release of preformed thyroid hormones from damaged thyroid cells. This is followed by a hypothyroid phase as thyroid hormone stores become depleted. Eventually, thyroid function may return to normal, though some patients develop permanent hypothyroidism. Hashimoto's thyroiditis, an autoimmune disorder, may present with or without symptoms of hypothyroidism, often featuring a painless goiter and elevated thyroid peroxidase antibodies.

Immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) are widely used as standard treatments for various tumor types. While ICIs are generally better tolerated than conventional chemotherapy, they are associated with unique immune-related toxicities, affecting multiple organs. The endocrine system is involved in up to 10% of cases, with the thyroid gland being the most frequently affected, leading to immune-induced destructive thyroiditis [2-4]. Destructive thyroiditis can also result from iodine exposure, such as iodinated contrast agents used in imaging [5, 6] or topical iodinated skin preparations [7]. At the same time, cancer patients undergoing ICI therapy often receive frequent CT scans with iodinated contrast or surgeries involving iodine-based antiseptics, such as povidone-iodine (Betadine). Additionally, ICI-induced overt hyperthyroidism has been observed more frequently in individuals with a higher body mass index [8]. However, the combined impact of these factors on thyroid dysfunction in a single patient has not been previously reported.

Case Report

We report a case of fulminant, painless destructive thyroiditis following a single dose of Pembrolizumab in a 72-year-old male veteran with diabetes mellitus, obesity, coronary artery disease, and recurrent desmoplastic melanoma. He received Pembrolizumab (2 mg/kg BW) on day 0. As illustrated in the accompanying figure, he underwent a left forearm skin biopsy prepped with Betadine on day -3 and two CT scans with oral and IV iodinated contrast on days 8 and 35.

The patient remained clinically euthyroid until day 22 after immunotherapy with lower

TSH [0.03 μ U/mL (normal range: 0.55–4.78)] and elevated FT4 [1.7 ng/dL (normal range: 0.67–1.52)]. He was severely obese, weighing 298 lbs (BMI 42.8). Throughout his clinical course, he reported no thyroid pain or discomfort. PET/CT and CT on days 8 and 35 showed “normal” thyroid gland. Severe hyperthyroidism (TSH = 0.01 μ U/mL, FT4 = 3.6 ng/dL) peaked at day 29. Thyroid-related antibody studies, including anti-TPO, anti-Tg, and TSI, were all negative. His serum cortisol level was within the normal range (12.9 μ g/dL; normal: 3–22.4 μ g/dL). Despite his condition, the patient was reluctant to receive treatment and took methimazole (10 mg/day) for only two days (days 35 and 36) without beta-blockers. Serum TSH remained low (0.03 μ U/mL) on day 51. He then experienced a rapid transition to hypothyroidism, with TSH levels rising to 35.5 μ U/mL (FT4 = 0.3 ng/dL) by day 72 and further to 97.4 μ U/mL (FT4 = 0.1 ng/dL) by day 99. Over the three-month period following Pembrolizumab administration, he exhibited minimal symptoms related to thyroid dysfunction, showing only slight weight loss and transient tachycardia (see Figure and Table).

He underwent a cycle of radiation therapy (XRT) to the right facial region from days 10 to 72 and initiated levothyroxine replacement on day 99. Pembrolizumab was not reintroduced during this period, but immune checkpoint inhibitor therapy was resumed on day 159, two months after LT4 replacement. On April 6, 2020—nearly eight months after receiving Pembrolizumab—a PET/CT scan revealed progression of right facial melanoma. He passed away three months later.

Figure: The vertical axis shows Serum TSH (uU/mL); the horizontal axis shows the time from 5/2015 to 5/2020. Days are numbered in reference to the date received a single dose of Pembrolizumab.

Long thin Arrow (\rightarrow): CT with iodinated contrast on 3/21/18, 9/28/18, 4/30/19, 8/20/19 (500 ml Omnipaque 300), 9/16/19, 1/3/20, 4/6/20, 5/28/20.

Short thin Arrow (\rightarrow): Right parotidectomy on 6/6/19, and Left forearm excisional biopsy on 8/9/19.

Short solid Arrow (\downarrow): Pembrolizumab treatment on 8/12/19 and then after 1/17/20. Solid arrowhead (\blacktriangledown) T4 replacement (0.1 mg/day) starts on Day 99 (11/19/19).

Table: Clinical course of TSH, FT4, weight and pulse rate in days before and after a single dose of Pembrolizumab treatment on 8/12/19.

Day	-3	0	8	10	22	29	35	42	51	72	99	119
TSH (mU/L)	1.01	1.76			0.03	0.01		0.01	0.03	35.49	97.37	59.76
FT4 (ng/dL)		-			1.7	3.6		1.2	1.4	0.3	0.1	0.9
Biopsy	Skin											
XRT				X		X	X	X	X	X	X	
ContrastCT			CT				CT					
Weight	304.3				303	295	282	289.5	293	293.3	297.6	300.2
Pulse Rate	79- 89	62- 65			76- 85	78-87	67-95	87	103	75- 91	64- 94	

Discussion

Like other organs, the thyroid gland can develop acute or chronic inflammation (1). In infectious and subacute thyroiditis, the gland is typically swollen and tender. However, in the present case, the patient reported neither swelling nor pain in the thyroid region. Riedel's thyroiditis, a rare chronic sclerosing condition, was unlikely, and the acute onset after a single dose of Pembrolizumab with negative TPO antibodies effectively ruled out chronic lymphocytic (Hashimoto's) thyroiditis.

Immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) have become the standard of care for various tumors. While generally better tolerated than conventional chemotherapy, ICIs can enhance immune responses affecting multiple organs. Among immune-related adverse events (irAEs), endocrine dysfunction occurs in up to 10% of cases [2]. Thyroid disorders, particularly reversible destructive thyroiditis and overt hypothyroidism, are the most frequently reported endocrine irAEs associated with ICIs, including Pembrolizumab [3]. The mechanism of thyroid destruction appears independent of antibodies, as demonstrated in this case (2), and may involve T-cell, NK-cell, and/or monocyte-mediated pathways [2-4].

Obesity is a proinflammatory metabolic state that may contribute to the development of ICI-associated irAEs [8]. Notably, overt thyrotoxicosis has been observed to occur earlier in obese patients compared to leaner individuals, as illustrated in the present case.

Overt hyperthyroidism can also result from destructive thyroiditis induced by iodinated contrast used in CT imaging or cardiac catheterization [5, 6, 9, 10]. The patient underwent CT scans with contrast on days 8 and 35, which may have increased the risk and severity of developing destructive thyroiditis. Typical doses for CT scans exceed 5 mg of bioavailable free iodine, with urinary iodine excretion remaining elevated for at least a month [11]. The patient received an oral preparation of Omnipaque on day 8 (500 mL, containing 150 g of organically bound iodine). Studies indicate that even 4.7 g of enterally administered iodine can sustain high urinary iodine levels for over 40 days [12].

Additionally, iodine can be absorbed through topical administration of povidone-iodine [7]. This patient underwent a skin biopsy three days before receiving Pembrolizumab, with Betadine used as a skin preparation. Although serum iodine levels were not measured in this patient, a prior case report documented a markedly elevated serum iodine concentration of 2,700 µg/dL (normal range: 4–9 µg/dL) following topical application of povidone-iodine [7]. Serum iodine levels remained elevated for up to seven days after discontinuation of povidone treatment. Thus, the topical Betadine use during the biopsy may have contributed to high circulating iodine levels and thyroid dysfunction.

The patient also received facial radiation therapy (RT) from days 10 through 72, which may have accelerated the transition from hyperthyroidism to hypothyroidism [13]. However, radiation-induced thyroid dysfunction typically takes years to manifest [14], whereas this case demonstrated a much more rapid onset.

Regardless of whether RT contributed to hypothyroidism, impaired thyroid function is associated with an increased overall risk of mortality [15, 16] and may have shortened this patient's lifespan.

Conclusions

Abnormal thyroid function is associated with higher mortality and reduced life expectancy. Thyroid dysfunction is the most common endocrine complication in cancer patients treated with ICIs. This case demonstrates the rapid progression of destructive thyroiditis following a single dose of pembrolizumab in an obese patient who had significant iodine

absorption through topical Betadine and CT studies with IV and oral iodinated contrast. Further studies are needed to better understand the role of iodine load in pembrolizumab-induced destructive thyroiditis with a fulminate course transitioning from thyrotoxicosis to severe hypothyroidism. Optimizing the metabolic state of cancer patients receiving immune checkpoint inhibitors may help reduce the incidence and severity of thyroid dysfunction, potentially improving overall survival and quality of life.

Sources of funding

This work was supported in part by the Department of Veterans Affairs.

Disclosure: None

References

1. Majety P, Hennessey JV. (2022) Acute and subacute, and Riedel's thyroiditis, edited by Feingold KR, Anawalt B, Blackman MR, et al., Endotex[Internet].
2. Spagnolo CC, Giuffrida G, Cannavò S, Franchina S, Silvestris N, Ruggeri RM, Santarpia M. (2023) Management of endocrine and metabolic toxicities of immune-checkpoint inhibitors: from clinical studies to a real life scenario. *Cancers*. 15: 246.
3. Delivanis DA, Gustafson MP, Bornschlegl S, Merten MM, Kottschade L, Withers S, Dietz AB, Ryder M. (2017) Pembrolizumab-Induced Thyroiditis: Comprehensive Clinical Review and Insights Into Underlying Involved Mechanisms. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 1;102: 2770-2780. doi: 10.1210/jc.2017-00448. PMID: 28609832
4. Fillete JD, Jansen Y, Schreuer M, Everaert H, Velkeniers B, Neyns B, Braverboer B. (2016) Incidence of thyroid-related adverse events in melanoma patients treated with pembrolizumab, *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 101: 4431-4439.
5. Calvi L, Daniels GH. (2011) Acute thyrotoxicosis secondary to destructive thyroiditis associated with cardiac catheterization contrast dye. *Thyroid*. 21: 443-9
6. Dunne P, Kaimal N, MacDonald J, Syed AA. (2013) Iodinated contrast-induced thyrotoxicosis, *CMAJ*. 185: 144-147.
7. Cruz FD, Brown DH, Leikin JB, Franklin C, Hryhorczuk DO. (1987) Iodine absorption after topical administration. *West J Med*. 146: 43-45
8. Pollack R, Ashash A, Cahn A, Rottenberg Y, Stern H, Dresner-Pollak R, Immune checkpoint inhibitor-induced thyroid dysfunction is associated with higher body mass index, *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 105: e3620-3627, <https://doi.org/10.1210/clinem/dgaa458>
9. Chambers, MD, Khan M, Chen C, Secrest S, Wu, SY. (2020) Marine-Lenhart Syndrome: role of iodinated contrast administration, case report and a review of literature, *J Med-Clin Res & Rev*. 4: 1-5.
10. Wu SY, Leung AM, Chambers MD, Chen CL, Kahn MU, Brent GA, Green WL. (2018) Coexistent Presentation of Graves' Disease and a Potentially Autonomous Thyroid Nodule Following Administration of an Iodinated Contrast Load, *J Clin Translat Endocrinol: Case Report*. 9: 1-3.
11. Nimmons GL, Frank GF, Graham MM, Pagedar NA. (2013) Urinary iodine excretion after contrast computed tomography scan, *JAMA Otolaryngo Head Neck Surg*. 139: 479-482.
12. Fassbender WJ, Vogel C, Doppl W, Stracke H, Bretzel RG, Klör HU. (2001) Thyroid Function, Thyroid Immunoglobulin Status, and Urinary Iodine Excretion after Enteral Contrast Agent Administration by Endoscopic Retrograde Cholangiopancreatography, *Endoscopy*. 33: 245-252. DOI: 10.1055/s-2001-12795.
13. Rooney MK, Andring LM, Corrigan KL, Bernard V, Williamson TD, Fuller CD, Garden AS, Gunn B, Lee A, Moreno AC, Spiotto M, Frank SJ, Morrison WH, Phan J, Rosenthal DI. (2023) Hypothyroidism following Radiotherapy for Head and Neck cancer: A Systematic Review of the Literature and Opportunities to Improve the Therapeutic Ra-

-
- tio. *Cancers*. 15: 4321. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers15174321>
14. Inoue E, Okajima K, Doi H, Fukuda K, Oguma Y, Ri A, Nishikawa D, Yane K, Matsuura T, Nishimura Y. (2021) Factors predictive of the development of hypothyroidism after intensity-modulated radiation therapy for pharyngeal cancer. *Acta Oto-Laryngologica*. 141:1022–1026. doi: 10.1080/00016489.2021.1998615. [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
15. Thvilum, M.; Brandt, F; Almind, D; Christensen, K.; Hegedüs, L.; Brix, T.H. (2013) Excess Mortality in Patients Diagnosed with Hypothyroidism: A Nationwide Cohort Study of Singletons and Twins. *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab*. 98: 1069–1075. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]
16. Wu SY, MD Chambers, Mazhar K, M Chinweze, TM Cao, HB Zhao. (2023) The etiology of abnormal TSH in veterans cared by a VA Medical Center – one high thyrotropin is associated with higher 5-years mortality. *J Endocrinol Disord*. 7: 133. DOI:10.31579/2045-1045/133 [CrossRef] [PubMed]

Cite this article: MARK CHAMBERS, MAZHAR KHAN, MAUREEN CHINWEZE, CONSTANCE CHEN, EDWARD FUA1, SING-YUNG WU. (2025) Hearing Voices: TFULMINANT DESTRUCTIVE PAINLESS THYROIDITIS AFTER A SINGLE DOSE OF PEMBROLIZUMAB IN AN OBESE ELDERLY MAN LOADED WITH IODINE. *Archives of Clinical Case Studies and Case Reports* 5(1): 345-348.

Copyright: ©2025 Sing-yung Wu. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.